

The Effect of Yoga on the Selected Motor Ability Components, Variables of Deaf and Dumb School Students of Pune City

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Abstract

Sport is one of the powerful and popular media that helps every one live sane a sanity. Man's life span is being determined by many factors among which physical activities stand atop. Social status, Economical Status and Health status have been improved through taking part in various competitions being organized by recognized bodies. Sport binds people from different walks despite caste, creed and religion. Taking part in sports and doing exercises help us to be free from diseases. Personality development, level of anxiety and other psychologies factors are developed by taking part in physical factors are developed by taking part in physical activities. A famous saying goes, "Brawn and Brain always together". Appetite and elimination process developed through exercise, which in turn help an individual to have a proper function of internal organs.

Introduction

Fitness is that state which characterizes the degree to which a person is able to function efficiently. It implies the ability of each person to live most effectively with his potentialities. According to vitals physical fitness can be referred as "the capacity of a person to function steadily and smoothly". A physically fit person feels mentally balanced, physically comfortable and is better able to take up the demands that everyday life makes upon him. Every individual should be physically fit to perform their daily work with ease and to take part in various activities. Hence it is better, not only to have efficiency in their daily work, but also a produce healthy citizen of the

Society. Physical fitness has been defined as "a readiness or preparedness of performance with special regard for big muscle activity without undue fatigue".

Yoga is an ancient art based on a harmonizing system of development for the body, mind and spirit. The continued practice of yoga will lead you to a sense of peace and wellbeing, and also a feeling of being at one with their environment. The practice of Yoga makes the body strong and flexible. It also improves the functioning of the respiratory, circulatory, digestive and hormonal systems. Yoga brings about emotional stability and clarity of mind.

It promotes the health of the endocrine glands which is associated with the nervous system and maintains the overall functional efficiency of the differential systems of the body. It puts certain groups of muscle tone which is closely related to one's own emotional behavior. By the practice of Yoga, we can change our reaction and our attitudes to stress. "Yoga brings oxygen and energy to every cell, cleans the organism by bringing out waste products expels the toxins while relaxation guards against neurasthenia and insomnia". Five positive benefits are as follows:

1. Establishing general muscular activity including the heart
2. Favorable effect on the psyche, especially as an antidote for mental strain.
3. Aids of digestive system and reducing nervous tension.
4. Control of obesity.
5. Sleeping in respiration which favors good gaseous exchange and makes the body become strong and healthy.

Deaf and Dumb School Students

The "Deaf and Dumb" (or even just "dumb", when applied to deaf people who do not speak) is an archaic term that is considered offensive. Many Deaf people do not use a spoken language; thus, they are technically "mute". The word "dumb" has at least an archaic meaning that means "mute". Of course, the word "dumb" also has another more common meaning now that implies stupidity, which is certainly not applicable to most Deaf people. Given the long history of deafness, and the fact that Deaf people have been incorrectly assumed to be mentally deficient just because they do not speak, you can imagine that most Deaf people do not appreciate being called "Deaf and Dumb". Going back to residential schools, these schools provide a vital link in the transmission

of Deaf Culture and Language. Children here are able to communicate in a language readily understood by each other. Deaf children are able to partake in social clubs, sports and importantly enough, to be around deaf role models. It is important for deaf children to be encouraged to further their education and to learn that deafness does not mean you cannot grow up to be successful and happy (success of course being at each persons own perspective on what success and happiness means to them individually). This is not to say that mainstream education is iniquitous for deaf children, but we must keep in mind that socialization is essential to a child's growth and without a common language socialization is limited.

Material and Method

In this research study experimental method used for measure effect of yogic program. In this study 30 school students who were studying Mahaveer Residential Deaf and Dumb School Urali-kanchan, Pune, were randomly chosen as subjects. They were divided into two groups, Group A (Fifteen Deaf and Dumb subjects) and Group B (Fifteen Deaf and Dumb subjects). The groups were designated as Group "A" (Control group) and Group "B" (Experimental group). The experimental group underwent Yogic training program for eight weeks and the subjects in control group were not engaged in any activity during this Yogic training period.

Selection of Variables

Table no. 1
Tools of data collection

Sr. No	Motor ability components	Test
1	Speed	50 meters Dash
2	Agility	4 x10 meters Shuttle Run

Table no. 2
Intra Class Reliability

Sr. No	Test	'R'
1	50 meters Dash	0.803
2	4 x10 meters Shuttle Run	0.769

Orientation of the Subjects

The investigator explained to the subjects participating in the study, the purpose of the Yogic training and their part in the study. For the collection of data, the investigator explained the procedure of the 50 meters dash test for speed, 4x10 meters shuttle run for agility and leg explosive power for standing broad jump and also instructed the subjects about the procedure to be adopted. Even though the control groups did not undergo any training, they were given a thorough knowledge about the test items followed in this study.

Yogic Training Programme

During the training period, the experimental group underwent yogic practice for five continuous days a week for eight weeks. Training included 30 minutes asanas in different postures and Pranayama for 5 minutes total time 35 minutes on each day for first four weeks. The remaining eight weeks for Yogic Training included 40 minutes asanas in different postures and pranayama for 10 minutes totally 50 minutes on every day. The subjects underwent their yogic training in the morning sessions from 6.15 am to 6.50 am for first four weeks, the remaining eight weeks from 6.15 a.m. to 7.05 a.m. under the supervision of the investigator.

Collection of Data

Pre-test data were collected three days before the training programme; post test data were collected three days after the yogic training programme. In all the cases, the data were collected on ten days in the morning and evening sessions.

Statistical Procedure

The data collected from the two groups were statistically examined for significant difference, if any, applying the analysis of covariance (ANCOVA). In all the cases 0.05 level of confidence was fixed as a level of confidence to test the hypothesis.

Result

Table-3
Analysis of Co Variance for the Pre-Test and Post-Test on Speed for Control and Experimental Groups (Scores in Second)

Test	Control Group	Experimental Group	Sources of variance	Sum of Squares	df	Mean squares	'F' value	Table Value
Pre-test Mean S.D.	7.181 0.395	7.094 0.324	Between Within	0.114 7.552	1 28	0.114 0.130	0.872	4.02
Post-test Mean S.D.	7.176 0.389	6.573 0.368	Between Within	5.466 8.313	1 28	5.466 0.143	38.137*	4.02
Adjusted Post Test Mean	7.133	6.161	Between Within	3.961 0.939	1 27	3.961 0.016	240.351*	4.01

* Significant at 0.05 Level

The table values required for significance at 0.05 level with df (1, 28) and (1, 27) were 4.02 and 4.01 respectively.

Since the obtained 'F' value 38.13 was higher than the table value 4.02, the result becomes significant and the hypothesis was accepted.

Table-4
Analysis of Co Variance for the Pre-Test and Post-Test on Agility for Control and Experimental Groups (Scores in Second)

Test	Control Group	Experimental Group	Sources of variance	Sum of Squares	df	Mean squares	'F' value	Table Value
Pre-test Mean S.D.	11.101 0.630	11.095 0.545	Between Within	0.000 20.126	1 28	0.0005 0.3470	0.0014	4.02
Post-test Mean S.D.	11.027 0.646	10.210 0.641	Between Within	10.012 23.995	1 28	10.0213 0.4137	24.2015*	4.02
Adjusted Post Test Mean	11.024	10.213	Between Within	9.875 3.357	1 27	9.875 0.076	129.1861*	4.01

* Significant at 0.05 Level

The table values required for significance at 0.05 level with df (1, 28) and (1, 27) were 4.02 and 4.01 respectively.

Since the obtained 'F' value 24.20 was higher than the table value 4.02, the result becomes significant and the hypothesis was accepted.

Conclusion

In the light of the findings and within the limitations of the present study the following conclusion was drawn.

Yoga group had significantly improved the selected motor ability components, (Speed and Agility) variables of deaf and dumb students.

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